

A new source of thermo-sensitive genic male sterility for 2-line hybrid rice breeding

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Scientists in Japan and at IRRI have reported a thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) line that shows complete pollen sterility at day/night temperatures of 31/24 °C and partial to complete fertility at 28/21 °C. Scientists in China, Japan, and at IRRI are attempting to use this male sterility system to develop two-line hybrids that are relatively easier to breed than three-line hybrids produced using the cytoplasmic genetic male sterility (CMS) system. To identify such genes from Indian germplasm for use in the two-line breeding system, we conducted a study at the Directorate of Rice Research.

Sixteen spontaneously occurring sterile plants from indica rice cultivar IET10726 were identified during 1990 kharif (wet) season. They had 100% pollen and spikelet sterility under a 30/18 °C regime and partial to complete fertility when the minimum temperature was higher (22 °C). One plant, MSM65-2, was selected for studying its fertility-sterility behavior under different temperature regimes in the field, glasshouse, and photoperiodic chambers.

The clones of this mutant showed differential behavior under different temperature regimes in the field and glasshouse, indicating the primary effect of temperature on sterility-fertility behavior (Table 1). The same clones, however, did not show differential sterility-fertility behavior in photoperiodic chambers, thus eliminating the possibility of daylength having any major effect in inducing sterility (Table 2).

The major role of temperature-induced male sterility was further elucidated during the 2nd wk after panicle initiation (PI) with MSM65-2 exhibiting 100% male sterility from 2nd wk of October to 1st wk of April when average minimum temperature was ≤ 22 °C at Hyderabad. It showed partial

Table 1. Pollen fertility-sterility behavior of male sterile mutant rice line under field and glasshouse conditions. Hyderabad, India, 1990.

Flowering date	Pollen sterility (%)	
	Field	Glasshouse
7 Nov	100 (20.1/30.8) ^a	15 (23.2/33.9)
8 Nov	100 (20.2/30.9)	16 (23.0/33.8)
9 Nov	100 (19.8/30.7)	12 (23.2/33.8)
10 Nov	100 (18.9/30.9)	16 (23.0/33.7)
11 Nov	100 (18.6/30.6)	11 (23.1/33.9)
12 Nov	100 (18.4/29.3)	12 (23.0/33.6)
13 Nov	100 (18.1/29.3)	10 (23.2/33.9)
14 Nov	100 (18.2/28.2)	15 (23.8/34.2)
15 Nov	100 (18.1/27.5)	10 (23.0/34.1)
16 Nov	100 (18.2/27.3)	8 (23.1/34.0)
17 Nov	100 (18.5/27.5)	10 (23.0/33.8)
18 Nov	100 (18.3/26.5)	95 (22.2/33.6)
19 Nov	100 (18.0/27.8)	100 (21.1/33.5)
20 Nov	100 (17.8/27.9)	100 (21.0/33.4)
21 Nov-14 Dec	100 (<18.0/<27.5)	100 (<21.0/<33.5)
Swarna (MTU7029) (control)	15 ^b	15 ^b

^aFigures in parentheses indicate corresponding average minimum/maximum temperature in °C during the critical week (2nd week after panicle initiation). ^bControl Swarna (MTU7029) showed pollen and spikelet sterility <15% in the field and glasshouse under different temperature regimes.

Table 2. Pollen fertility-sterility behavior of mutant rice line in the field and in photoperiodic chambers. Hyderabad, India.

Flowering date	Pollen sterility (%)		
	Field	Photoperiodic chamber (12-h photoperiod)	Photoperiodic chamber (14-h photoperiod)
1 Feb	100 (12.1/27.9) ^a	100 (20.8/35.6)	100 (20.7/35.7)
2 Feb	100 (12.1/28.3)	100 (20.8/34.9)	100 (20.7/34.9)
3 Feb	100 (11.9/28.6)	100 (20.7/34.4)	100 (20.6/34.5)
4 Feb	100 (11.8/28.2)	100 (21.3/33.8)	100 (21.2/33.9)
5 Feb	100 (12.1/29.2)	100 (21.2/33.6)	100 (21.8/33.8)
6 Feb	100 (12.1/29.4)	100 (21.4/33.6)	100 (21.5/33.7)
7 Feb	100 (12.4/29.6)	100 (21.4/33.8)	100 (21.6/33.4)
8 Feb	100 (12.8/30.0)	100 (21.6/33.9)	100 (21.6/34.1)
9 Feb	100 (13.0/30.1)	8 (22.1/33.8)	12 (22.2/34.1)
10 Feb	100 (12.8/30.0)	10 (22.4/33.9)	10 (22.5/34.0)
11 Feb	100 (12.9/29.9)	9 (22.9/34.2)	10 (22.8/34.3)
12 Feb	100 (13.0/29.7)	10 (23.4/34.2)	7 (23.4/34.4)
13 Feb	100 (12.1/29.8)	10 (23.5/34.1)	5 (23.5/34.2)
14 Feb	100 (12.2/30.1)	8 (23.7/34.0)	6 (23.5/34.2)
15 - 20 Feb	100 (<12.8/<30.2)	9 (>23.6/>34.1)	8 (>23.4/>34.1)
Swarna (MTU7029) (control)	15 ^b	15 ^b	15 ^b

^aFigures in parentheses indicate corresponding average minimum/maximum temperature in °C during the critical (2nd week after panicle initiation). ^bControl Swarna (MTU7029) showed pollen and sterility <15% in the field and photoperiodic chambers under different temperature regimes.

to complete fertility during the rest of the year. The mutant's angle and duration of glume opening were comparable with those of CMS line V20 A. We assessed this mutant's potential by crossing it with genotypes exhibiting fertility even at 20/16 °C. The resulting two-line hybrids were evaluated during 1992 rabi (dry) season and found to be heterotic.

The TGMS line, when grown in a fertility-inducing temperature regime, can be multiplied by selfing without using a

B line, which is essential for multiplication of a CMS line. The two-line system has an advantage over the CMS system because rice varieties without the fertility restoration gene can be used effectively in a hybrid rice development program. ■